

A DESIGN OF INTELLIGENT WEARABLE HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM BASED ON IOT

Akula Venkata Ashish¹, Koduru Rushika²,
Kuchani Abhinaya³, Mr. S. Gopala Krishna⁴

^{1,2,3} UG Student, Dept. of ECE, CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

⁴ Assistant Professor, Dept. of ECE,
CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

ABSTRACT

Based on the Internet of things and micro-control chip technology, this paper designed a wearable health monitoring system for multi-function (mainly for lungwheezing), and introduced ZigBee multifunction (mainly for lung-wheezing), and introduced ZigBee protocol and CC2530. While most current health monitoring devices monitor heart rate, body temperature, and falls, very few are available for asthmatic wheezing, which largely due to the difficulty of filtering the frequency of wheezing.

INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things is a new information technology that connects any object to the Internet via a sensor and protocol for information exchange and communication. Wearable-monitoring system is an inevitable product of the development and maturity of the IoT. The combination of IoT technology and sensor technology construct a wearable health monitoring system to monitor the changes of the vital signs of the user. In fact, a number of scientists have developed fully functional devices and put them on the market. After 2000, China's telemedicine health monitoring system entered a stage of rapid development. During this period, due to the rapid popularization of Internet technology and the development of information technology, many companies

and scientific research institutions have made beneficial explorations in telemedicine. In recent years, there has been a trend of research on physiological data monitoring device in China. Shanghai Jiao Tong University, for example, has made a breakthrough in mobile blood pressure measurements. The most common monitoring systems are heart rate measurement, fall alarm, temperature monitoring, while the monitoring system studied in this paper is a wearable device based on IoT and multi-function (mainly for asthma) monitoring. With the enrichment of material life in modern society, people start to pay more attention to their health, which leads to the need for health monitoring. Taking the patients with chronic diseases such as asthma as an example, condition of the continuous and automatic monitoring of the respiratory system is crucial. Unfortunately, this diagnostic information is not gainable unless patients are monitored in the hospital. Stethoscope auscultation has been the most commonly used respiratory monitoring method for many years. However, this is not an ideal way to continuously monitor breathing conditions.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Sang Shiqing, Ge Xiulong. Design and implementation of remote health monitoring system based on Internet of

things [J]. New technologies and products of China,2014(20):12-14.

Even though large-scale projects, such as sea-crossing bridges and tunnels, have complex structures and service conditions, the structural health monitoring (SHM) system can comprehensively monitor the stress situation and damage evolution law in the entire construction and service process of such structures. Based on the background of the Hong Kong–Zhuhai–Macao Bridge, this study systematically introduces the overall goal and framework of the SHM system, monitoring content, and sensor information. Moreover, the structural health condition evaluation methods and data analysis methods are presented in detail. Then, on the basis of a multilayer data storage system, a fault-tolerant data center platform design, an open integrated supervision platform design, and other measures, a set of reliable and advanced large-scale software systems are built to achieve the SHM system for the Hong Kong–Zhuhai–Macao Bridge. Finally, the wind characteristics around the Hong Kong–Zhuhai–Macao Bridge and some of the monitored structural responses from the Super Typhoon Mangkhut in 2018 are shown, which verified that the SHM system can accurately and reliably monitor and feedback the environmental load and structural response of the principal parts of the Hong Kong–Zhuhai–Macao Bridge under complicated service environment. Societal and economic development has led to the continuous construction of large-span bridges and underground tunnels over rivers, lakes, and seas. These projects are large in scale and structurally complex and have harsh service environment. Compared with underground tunnels, a bridge structure is more lightweight and flexible. However, it

easily suffers from frequent traffic loads, fluctuating wind loads, rainstorm attacks, and temperature effects. Structural performance can easily degrade under the above loads or actions, posing a risk to the safe operation of the structure and even causing collapsed accidents [1–4].

Salaheldin Mohamed Ibrahim Edam. Key Technologies of Wireless Ad-hoc and Sensor Networks for Optimized Transmission Management in Disaster Situation[D]. Beijing University of Posts and Telecommunications,2014.

At present, sensor networks and the Internet of Things have made rapid development and received more and more attention. Wireless sensor network technology is widely applied in many industries. As an important part of IoT sensor layer, it is an important infrastructure for IoT development. The purpose of this paper is to enhance the existing wireless sensor networks on the basis of existing technologies for better application in IoT. In this article, we introduce the structural features, key techniques, and some specific applications of wireless sensor networks in the IoT. Secondly, this paper studies and analyzes the principle of the cell membrane algorithm and its own characteristics. Aiming at the problem of energy constraint in wireless sensor network, an energy equilibrium clustering algorithm based on the cell membrane optimization algorithm is proposed in order to realize energy balance of nodes and distribution of network cluster heads. This algorithm divides the nodes by concentration and energy factors and divides them into globally balanced clusters by combining distance factors, which can well solve the problems of uneven distribution of

cluster heads and unbalanced global power usage in sensor networks. On the basis of a lot of previous researches, this paper presents a QoS model, which is based on the routing protocol, clustering protocol, and data fusion scheme discussed in this paper. Through analysis and experiments, it is proved that this scheme improves energy consumption and flexibility by 78% compared with the previous one and achieves better network performance. The so-called IoT, which is something connected to the Internet, founded in 2009 in China “experience China” center, and also, developing the IoT of the national IoT “twelfth five-year” development plan is also in the process of development; this move is to determine that IoT has an irreplaceable role in the new era, which is a significant position in the emerging technology sector. Wireless sensor network technology, as the backbone of the Internet of Things, needs continuous development to promote the whole IoT and even Huliang network and becomes a catalyst for global economic development.

Zhu chunxiang, Chen ruan, CAI hu, et al. Wearable physiological parameter monitoring system based on ZigBee network [J]. Biomedical engineering research, 2019, 38 (01) : 116-119.

The design and development of a Zigbee smart noninvasive wearable physiological parameters monitoring device has been developed and reported in this paper. The system can be used to monitor physiological parameters, such as temperature and heart rate, of a human subject. The system consists of an electronic device which is worn on the wrist and finger, by an at-risk person. Using several sensors to measure different vital signs, the person is wirelessly monitored

within his own home. An impact sensor has been used to detect falls. The device detects if a person is medically distressed and sends an alarm to a receiver unit that is connected to a computer. This sets off an alarm, allowing help to be provided to the user. The device is battery powered for use outdoors. The device can be easily adapted to monitor athletes and infants. The low cost of the device will help to lower the cost of home monitoring of patients recovering from illness. A prototype of the device has been fabricated and extensively tested with very good results. wireless sensors and sensor networks have become a great interest to research, scientific and technological community. Though sensor networks have been in place for more than a few decades now, the wireless domain has opened up a whole new application space of sensors. Wireless sensors and sensor networks are different from traditional wireless networks as well computer networks and, therefore, pose more challenges to solve such as limited energy, restricted life time, etc. [1]. Wireless sensing units integrate wireless communications and mobile computing with transducers to deliver a sensor platform which is inexpensive to install in numerous applications. Indeed, co-locating computational power and radio frequency (RF) communication within the sensor unit itself is a distinct feature of wireless sensing.

Block diagram

ARUDINO

The Arduino is a family of microcontroller boards to simplify electronic design, prototyping and experimenting for artists, hackers, hobbyists, but also many professionals. People use it as brains for their robots, to build new digital music instruments, or to build a system that lets your house plants tweet you when they're dry. Arduinos (we use the standard Arduino Uno) are built around an ATmega microcontroller — essentially a complete computer with CPU, RAM, Flash memory, and input/output pins, all on a single chip. Unlike, say, a Raspberry Pi, it's designed to attach all kinds of sensors, LEDs, small motors and speakers, servos, etc. directly to these pins, which can read in or output digital or analog voltages between 0 and 5 volts. The Arduino connects to your computer via USB, where you program it in a simple language (C/C++, similar to Java) from inside the free

Arduino IDE by uploading your compiled code to the board. Once programmed, the Arduino can run with the USB link back to your computer, or stand-alone without it — no keyboard or screen needed, just power.

Heart beat

The front of the sensor, with the heart logo, is where you put your finger. You'll also notice a tiny circular opening through which the Kingbright's reverse mounted green LED shines. Just beneath the circular opening is a small ambient light photo sensor – [APDS-9008](#) from Avago. This sensor is similar to the ones used in cell phones, tablets, and laptops to adjust the screen's brightness based on the ambient lighting conditions.

DHT TEMPERATURE & HUMIDITY SENSORS.

These sensors are very basic and slow, but are great for hobbyists who want to do some basic data logging. The DHT sensors are made of two parts, a capacitive humidity sensor and a thermistor. There is also a very basic chip inside that does some analog to digital conversion and spits out a digital signal with the temperature and humidity. The digital signal is fairly easy to read using any microcontroller. Humidity is the measure of water vapour present in the air. The level of

humidity in air affects various physical, chemical and biological processes. In industrial applications, humidity can affect the business cost of the products, health and safety of the employees. So, in semiconductor industries and control system industries measurement of humidity is very important. Humidity measurement determines the amount of moisture present in the gas that can be a mixture of water vapour, nitrogen, argon or pure gas etc... Humidity sensors are of two types based on their measurement units. They are a relative humidity sensor and Absolute humidity sensor. DHT11 is a digital temperature and humidity sensor.

MEMS:

Microelectromechanical systems (MEMS), also written as micro-electro-mechanical systems (or microelectronic and microelectromechanical systems) and the related micro mechatronics and microsystems constitute the technology of microscopic devices, particularly those with moving parts. They merge at the nanoscale into nanoelectromechanical systems (NEMS) and nanotechnology. MEMS are also referred to as micromachines in Japan and microsystem technology (MST) in Europe. MEMS are made up of components between 1 and 100 micrometers in size (i.e., 0.001 to 0.1 mm), and MEMS devices generally range

in size from 20 micro metres to a millimetre (i.e., 0.02 to 1.0 mm), although components arranged in arrays (e.g., digital micromirror devices) can be more than 1000 mm². [1] They usually consist of a central unit that processes data (an integrated circuit chip such as microprocessor) and several components that interact with the surroundings (such as microsensors). [2] Because of the large surface area to volume ratio of MEMS, forces produced by ambient electromagnetism (e.g., electrostatic charges and magnetic moments), and fluid dynamics (e.g., surface tension and viscosity) are more important design considerations than with larger scale mechanical devices. MEMS technology is distinguished from molecular nanotechnology or molecular electronics in that the latter must also consider surface chemistry. The potential of very small machines was appreciated before the technology existed that could make them (see, for example, Richard Feynman's famous 1959 lecture *There's Plenty of Room at the Bottom*). MEMS became practical once they could be fabricated using modified semiconductor device fabrication technologies, normally used to make electronics. [3] These include molding and plating, wet etching (KOH, TMAH) and dry etching (RIE and DRIE), electrical discharge

machining (EDM), and other technologies capable of manufacturing small devices.

BUZZERS

In common parlance a Buzzer is a signaling device that is not a loudspeaker. It can be mechanical, electromechanical, or electronic (a piezo transducer). BeStar produces Buzzers in every available configuration for a wide variety of applications. A Piezo transducer can produce the sound for panel mount buzzers, household goods, medical devices and even very loud sirens. When a lower frequency is required an electromagnetic buzzer can fill the need. These are very common in automotive chimes and higher end clinical diagnostic devices. The BeStar buzzer range includes self drive units with their own drive circuitry (indicators), or external drive units, which allow the designer the flexibility to create their own sound patterns.

ESP8266

The ESP8266 is a low-cost Wi-Fi microchip, with a full TCP/IP stack and microcontroller capability, produced by Espressif Systems[1] in Shanghai, China. The chip first came to the attention of Western makers in August 2014 with the ESP-01 module, made by a third-party manufacturer Ai-Thinker. This small

module allows microcontrollers to connect to a Wi-Fi network and make simple TCP/IP connections using Hayes-style commands. However, at first there was almost no English-language documentation on the chip and the commands it accepted.[2] The very low price and the fact that there were very few external components on the module, which suggested that it could eventually be very inexpensive in volume, attracted many hackers to explore the module, the chip, and the software on it, as well as to translate the Chinese documentation.[3] The ESP8285 is an ESP8266 with 1 MiB of built-in flash, allowing the building of single-chip devices capable of connecting to Wi-Fi.[4] The successors to these microcontroller chips is the ESP32 family of chips, including the pin-compatible ESP32-C3.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a wearable health monitoring device for asthma is designed, which can be used for early diagnosis as well as recording long-term asthma symptoms to help doctors diagnose it. This system designed the hardware part of this system and the transmission process, including the wheeze detection module and body motion detection module, with CC2530 as the main control system, connected with the upper computer through the MAX3485CAP level conversion chip, using ZigBee technology star topology.

However, due to the lack of clinical data, there are few studies on wheezing, and no specific data on the lung noise signals of asthmatic patients, it is not yet possible to obtain accurate algorithms to improve the system.

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